

THE ROLE OF THE NATIONAL IDEA IN IMPROVING THE SPIRITUALITY OF YOUTH

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Abstract: This article analyzes the role of the national idea in enhancing the spirituality of youth, emphasizing its educational and social importance. It highlights how the national idea shapes young people's worldview, instills patriotism, humanism, and tolerance. The paper also discusses the significance of cooperation between education, family, and community in fostering spiritual development among youth.

Keywords: National idea, spirituality, youth, education, patriotism, values, enlightenment, ideological upbringing.

In today's era of globalization, the issue of raising the spirituality of youth is more important than ever. Because the worldview, life position and social activity of the younger generation determine the future prospects of the country. Therefore, the role of the national idea and the science of the foundations of spirituality in ensuring the spiritual well-being of young people in Uzbekistan is incomparable. The national idea is an ideological force that unites the dreams and hopes, historical memory and spiritual values of the people, encouraging them towards development. It plays an important role in educating young people in the spirit of high human qualities such as goodness, patriotism, honesty, and tolerance. During the years of independence, on the initiative of our President, large-scale reforms were implemented aimed at educating young people as comprehensively mature, modern-thinking individuals based on the national idea. Conceptual ideas such as "High spirituality is an invincible force" and "From national revival to national advancement" serve as a theoretical and practical foundation in this direction. This article analyzes the role of the national idea in raising the spirituality of youth, its educational and social significance, as well as its inextricable connection with national values. The national idea, in its content and essence, relies on national-spiritual values. The national idea is manifested as a factor of national development and is reflected in national-spiritual values. Such an integral connection enhances the influence of the national idea. Undoubtedly, the role of national-spiritual values, language, customs, traditions, religion, writing, art, music, architecture, folk philosophy, worldview, artistic and oral creativity in the formation of the national idea is very large. "...the most important task facing us now," emphasizes our Head of State, "is to place the essence of the

principles of the perfect person, social cooperation, interethnic harmony, and interreligious tolerance, which constitute integral components of our national idea, at the center of the spiritual, educational, and upbringing work being carried out in our country today, to raise them to a new level, and to educate our young generation as independent thinkers with mature worldviews."After gaining independence, the influence of national and spiritual values in Uzbekistan has been increasing. In particular, it would not be wrong to say that people's respect for national and spiritual values is very high. In a more extensive study of the inextricable link between the national idea and national and spiritual values, Islam Karimov's "Uzbekistan: On the Threshold of the 21st Century: Threats to Security, Conditions for Stability and Guarantees of Development" is worth mentioning. It would not be wrong to say that this work fully reveals the essence of the restoration of spiritual values and the awareness of national identity. First of all, this work is based on the fact that the restoration of spiritual values should be considered an integral, natural process consisting of the growth of the awareness of national identity, the return of the people to their roots, to their roots. Secondly, the work reflects the necessary level of analysis of the fact that the restoration and restoration of spiritual values, as well as religious values and traditions sacred to our people, and the realization of our identity took place in rather difficult conditions – in a situation where the old imperial system collapsed and new social relations were being established. Thirdly, it is emphasized that the spiritual awakening of our people, along with the ethnic, cultural and religious tolerance, is an inexhaustible source of spiritual values, the etiquette of traditional family and kinship relations. "The restoration of spiritual values," says Islam Karimov, "also means their adaptation to the capabilities of the modern world and information civilization."In this work, Islam Karimov put forward the following ideas about the revival of spiritual values and awareness of national identity. Karimov I.A. High spirituality is an invincible force. Karimov I.A. Uzbekistan on the threshold of the 21st century; threats to security, conditions for stability and guarantees of development. Despite the long-standing severe ideological pressure, the people of Uzbekistan managed to preserve their historical and cultural values and their unique traditions, passed down from generation to generation; Having gained political independence and freedom, our people became the true masters of their own destiny, the creators of their own history, and the owners of their own national culture; History is becoming a true education of the nation; Due to the beginning of the reform and renewal of social life, powerful layers of spiritual culture have been revealed, and attention to

democratic values is increasing; “No society can imagine its future without developing and strengthening spiritual values,” says our Head of State. At the beginning of the presentation of the issue of “Recognition of universal human values and national characteristics in the national idea,” it is appropriate to provide students with brief information about the principles of the priority of universal human values. The principles of the priority of universal human values are a set of activities based on ideas based on the priority of material and cultural phenomena, criteria, and valuable aspects that are of positive significance for all peoples and correspond to the common interests of humanity. It is known that every person, regardless of gender, race, nationality, age, profession, or faith, is first and foremost a human being, a human being. This common essence makes it possible to distinguish objects, phenomena, processes, and relationships that are equally important and valuable for all people and nations. First of all, universal human values represent the integrity of human history, which, along with the passage of time and changes in social life, are further improved and developed, increasingly becoming a force that brings peoples, nations, and people closer together, unites, and perfects. Secondly, universal and national values are inextricably linked and mutually enrich each other through interaction. National values that have acquired universal significance become important values for all peoples. Therefore, universal values are inherently broader than national values and belong to humanity by origin. Thirdly, universality is manifested through national and personal values. The priority of universality is based on the requirement that every person be happy and prosperous, and that all good deeds, changes and reforms carried out in society should serve the interests of man. Fourthly, the position of each nation is measured by its contribution to the development of humanity. Contrasting national and universal values can lead to negative consequences. Thus, the respectful recognition and acceptance of values of universal significance, regardless of where and when they were formed and by which nation they were created, only serves development. Therefore, it is not for nothing that in our independent Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the commonality of national and universal values, and our people follow the path of development together with the world community. “The source of strength and power of independent Uzbekistan is the loyalty of our people to universal values,” says our Head of State. This treatise thoroughly analyzes the fact that our people have been nurturing the delicate buds of justice, equality, good neighborliness and humanity for centuries, that the goal of renewing society is to restore national

and universal traditions, and that humanity is an integral quality of the national spirit of the Uzbek people.

In his speech at the first session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 23, 1995, President Islam Karimov analyzed, based on a new methodology, that high spirituality is the foundation of the future. "The fate of development is decided by spiritually mature people," he says. Humanism and social justice Stability and prosperity Kindness and progress Freedom and liberty Our Head of State also emphasized in his speech that economic recovery, economic revival, economic development are completely in harmony with the efforts of spiritual recovery, spiritual purification, and spiritual elevation. In 1997, our Head of State spoke about the need to develop and implement a set of complementary political, economic, and cultural programs aimed at strengthening the positive, creative essence of spiritual revival, and reiterated that these programs are based, first of all, on a differentiated approach to the reviving heritage, the need to select morally significant traditions and customs that enrich the most important, universal human values, and meet the requirements of democratization and renewal of our society. "The revival of the Spirit of the Uzbek people, the formation of the spiritual and moral ideals of the nation are phenomena closely related to deep nationalism and universal humanity," says Islam Karimov. When talking about "the importance of basing the national idea on national and spiritual values," it is first necessary to briefly dwell on the fact that the impact of the national idea on society depends to a greater or lesser extent on its foundation on national and spiritual values. In order for this or that idea to emerge as a national idea and have an impact, it must be based on national values, traditions, and be related to issues related to the past, present, and future of the nation. Therefore, only when the national idea is directly related to the past and current state of the nation, can it set the goals and objectives that the nation must achieve in the long or historically short term. Can express it correctly.

The national idea is an important ideological basis for the formation of youth spirituality. It encourages young people to realize their national identity, to serve the Motherland with love and devotion. Analysis shows that the education system, family and neighborhood cooperation, and the positive influence of the media are important for the national idea to be firmly established in the hearts of young people. The spiritual maturity of young people is not only a guarantee of personal perfection, but also a guarantee of the sustainable development of society. Therefore, educating young people in the spirit of a perfect person based on the

national idea is one of the most important tasks that ensure the spiritual and political strength of Uzbekistan. In the future, in-depth scientific study of the issues of the national idea and spiritual education, their implementation in the education system based on modern methods will serve as an important factor in raising the younger generation as loyal, strong-willed, selfless individuals committed to national and universal values.

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